

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_GT_001_022.fcs
Aggregates
43582

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_GT_2_001_023.fcs
Aggregates
42508

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_GT_2_011.fcs
Aggregates
42531

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_GT_3_001_024.fcs
Aggregates
42532

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_GT_3_012.fcs
Aggregates
43077

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_GT_010.fcs
Aggregates
43129

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_001_019.fcs
Aggregates
43275

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_2_001_020.fcs
Aggregates
43095

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_2_008.fcs
Aggregates
43242

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_3_001_021.fcs
Aggregates
43784

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_3_009.fcs
Aggregates
44056

Specimen_002_GolgiTag_007.fcs
Aggregates
43489

Specimen_002_HA_empty_GT_001_016.fcs
Aggregates
42729

Specimen_002_HA_empty_GT_2_001_017.fcs
Aggregates
42895

Specimen_002_HA_empty_GT_2_005.fcs
Aggregates
42892

Specimen_002_HA_empty_GT_3_001_018.fcs
Aggregates
42087

Specimen_002_HA_empty_GT_3_006.fcs
Aggregates
42273

Specimen_002_HA_empty_GT_004.fcs
Aggregates
43059

Specimen_002_HA_empty_001_013.fcs
Aggregates
42177

Specimen_002_HA_empty_001.fcs
Aggregates
42375

Specimen_002_HA_empty_2_001_014.fcs
Aggregates
40814

Specimen_002_HA_empty_2_002.fcs
Aggregates
41071

Specimen_002_HA_empty_3_001_015.fcs
Aggregates
42032

Specimen_002_HA_empty_3_003.fcs
Aggregates
42268

